

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Highlights of 1975 International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) Nurseries

The International Rice Yield Nursery (IRYN) was broadly divided into early and medium maturity groups. In the early group (nine countries, 27 trials), W6-1899-25-4, IR2061-465-1-5-5, IR2061-628-1-64, and IR2071-625-1-252 performed well at most locations. In the medium-duration group (eight countries, 21 locations), Biplab, BM2-87-1, BR51-91-6, and BG90-2 performed well.

Results from the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) are indicative of resistance of some entries to some of the major diseases at most locations (see table).

In the upland yield nursery (five countries, 19 locations), IR1 529-430-3, IR2035-242-1, and BPI 76⁹/Dawn (IR9575) produced the highest overall yields. Most test sites were in the Philippines (11 locations) and India (five locations). The highest average yields for the Philippine locations were from IR1 529-430-3 and IR2035-242-1; the highest yields for the Indian locations were from IET 1444.

Twenty entries in the blast nursery showed resistance to blast at more than 15 of the 22 reporting locations (see table). Most of them derived their resistance from Tetep. Twelve were semidwarfs. Analysis of sheath blight

E. Heinrichs (IRRI), S. Pongprasert (Thailand), and P. Rao (India) check gall midge incidence in IRTP regional monitoring tour in Thailand.

nursery results for the past 3 years showed that seven entries displayed consistent, moderately resistant reactions: five semidwarfs (Bahagia, IR1544-340-6, IR32-76-67P, K8 mutant selection, and Pankaj) and two tall varieties (Laka and Ta-poo-choo-z). Eighteen varieties in the tungro nursery exhibited resistance to tungro at most of the eight test sites in five countries (see table). Significantly, 11 of these entries were accessions from the Assam Rice Collection.

Gangala, Ptb 19, Ptb 21, and ARC 6650 displayed resistance to brown planthopper under greenhouse conditions at nine of 11 test locations in five countries; however, such resistance does not fit into either the *Bph 1* or *bph 2* groups. Twenty-one other entries exhibited resistance of known gene sources: nine to the *Bph 1* type (as in IR26, Mudgo, and RP9-6) and 12 to the *bph 2* type (as in Chianung-sen-yu 11, CR94-13, and H 105).

In screening for salinity tolerance in the Philippines, Thailand, and India, three varieties were identified as promising: Pokkali, DA-29, and Nona Bokra.

Entries that were found resistant to three major diseases in the 1975 International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) nurseries, IRRI, 1975.

Blast ^a	Varieties resistant to	
	Bacterial blight	Tungro
<i>IRON</i> ^b	<i>IRON</i>	<i>IRON</i>
IR1544-181-1-1	BR51-49-6	IR2071-542-3-1
IR1820-210-2	BR51-67-1/C1	IR2863-31-3
IR2588-60-1	IR2053-362-14-4	IR2863-38-1
IR2588-132-1-2	IR2053-375-1-1-5	IRTN ^d
IR2793-80-1	IR2055-481-2-6-2	Ptb 8
IR2798-88-3	IR2793-80-1	ARC 13820
IR2798-88-3	IR2863-22-3	ARC 13901
IR2811-24-3	IR2863-31-3	ARC 13959
IR2851-41-3	IR286348-2	ARC 10342
<i>IRBN</i> ^c	IR2071-636-5-5	Habiganj DW 8
CICA 4//IR665-23-3-1/Tetep	IR2070-423-2-5-6	ARC 7125
IR665-23-3-1//IR841-65/C46-15	R32	ARC 13677
IR665-23-3-1//IR665-33/Tetep		Kataribhog (India)
IR29		DWA8
IR1520-52-2-4-1		ARC 7318
IR2035-255-2-3-2		ARC 10531
IR2058-435-3-2-2-2		Kataribhog (26683)
IR2588-2-3-3		SLO12
IR2793-10-2		ARC 7140
IR2793-38-3		ARC 13560
IR2793-80-1		Ambemohar 159
Washabo (SML 56/7)		
Raminad Strain 3		
IR1416-128-5-8		
CA 435-b-5-1		
CA 902-b-3-3		
Carreon		
PI 184675-2		
Ta-poo-choo-z		
Tetep		

^aVarieties listed as resistant to blast under IRON showed resistance to both leaf and neck blast.

^bIRON: International Rice Observational Nursery.

^cIRBN: International Rice Blast Nursery (tested only for leaf blast).

^dIRTN: International Rice Tungro Nursery.